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CARDIOVASCULAR COMPLICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH SEVERE PNEUMONIA WITH INFLUENZA A/H1N1/09

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Abstract: Aim of the study was to analyze the frequency and nature of cardiovascular complications in influenza A/H1N1/09.

Material and methods. 86 cases of severe influenza A/H1N1/09 were analyzed.

Results. The patients were divided into 2 groups, comparable by gender and age. The first group consisted of patients with cardiovascular complications of influenza A/H1N1/09 (41 people). The second group consisted of patients without complicated flu (45 people). The average age of patients in the first group was 60±13.7 years. According to the ECG results, sinus tachycardia with a heart rate of 94 14.2 beats/min was dominant, in combination with various rhythm and conduction disorders: supraventricular extrasystole in 5 (12%) patients, acute (paroxysmal) atrial fibrillation in 19 (46%), ventricular extrasystole in 7 (17%), complete right and left bundle branch block in 7 (17%) and 7 (17%), respectively, atrioventricular block of the 1st degree in 1 (2%) patients. Long QT syndrome was revealed in 5 patients (12%). The severe cardiovascular system complications were: myopericarditis in 2 (5%) people, decompensation of chronic heart failure in 4 (10%) people, pulmonary embolism in 1 (2%), acute myocardial infarction in 11 (27%). The mortality rate in this group was 12 (29%) cases from hospitalized patients. The average age of patients in the second group was 58 14.1 years. According to the ECG results, sinus tachycardia with a heart rate of 919.4 beats/min was detected in 98% of cases, 3 (7%) patients had complete left bundle branch block, 1 (2%) patient had atrial fibrillation. No other rhythm or conduction disturbances were detected. No organic heart pathology

was detected in this group of patients. The mortality rate was 5 (11%) people. Conclusion. The analysis of 86 cases showed that elderly patients with a heavy premorbid background prevailed. The severe cardiovascular system complications were mainly represented by cardiac arrhythmias and the development of acute myocardial infarction. The fatal outcome occurred on the 8th-22nd day from the onset of the disease. The presence of cardiovascular complications doubles the mortality rate.

Keywords: influenza, pneumonia, arrhythmias, myocarditis.

Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases account for approximately 30% of diseases worldwide. In addition to traditional risk factors (hypertension, smoking, diabetes mellitus, obesity, physical inactivity, dyslipidemia), influenza infection has long been considered a direct contributor to cardiovascular morbidity and mortality [1]. Various infectious agents are involved in the development and progression of atherosclerosis, and influenza virus RNA has been detected in human atherosclerotic plaques. Experimental reports indicate that influenza infections can cause direct cardiac injury, ranging from asymptomatic ECG abnormalities to myopericarditis and acute myocardial infarction, and have systemic effects through inflammatory cytokines and prothrombotic changes that may lead to population-wide increases in cardiovascular hospitalizations and mortality [2, 3]. In temperate regions, influenza epidemics recur annually in winter and coincide with sharp increases in cardiovascular mortality. This timing may provide a basis for active public health mitigation efforts. The most common complication that determines the severity of the disease is pneumonia. Influenza infection complicated by pneumonia in the early stages has a severe course with the development of cardiovascular and respiratory failure [4, 5]. The aim of this study is to analyze the frequency and nature of cardiovascular complications in influenza A/H1N1/09.

Material and methods

A total of 86 cases of severe influenza A/H1N1/09 were analyzed. The diagnosis was confirmed by PCR: antemortem in nasopharyngeal swabs, postmortem in autopsy tissue materials. The diagnoses were established in accordance with the joint recommendations of the European Respiratory Society (ERS) / European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (ECCMID), 2011.

To identify individuals with severe community-acquired pneumonia, the American Thoracic Society / Infectious Diseases Society of America criteria, the SMART-COP scale and its modifications were used. Patients received antiviral drugs, antibiotics, additional respiratory support or artificial ventilation. Treatment of concomitant cardiac pathology was carried out with beta-blockers, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, antiarrhythmic and diuretic drugs, antiplatelet agents, and anticoagulants. Inclusion criteria for the study: adult patients of both sexes with a diagnosis of community-acquired pneumonia against the background of influenza A/H1N1/09, who did not receive outpatient therapy, and were not vaccinated against influenza. Exclusion criteria: pregnancy, the presence of acquired immunodeficiency syndrome and other immunodeficiency states.

The obtained data are presented as absolute and relative values, arithmetic mean and standard deviation. To compare the indicators, the Pearson χ^2 criterion or Fisher criterion, calculation of the relative risk (OR), as well as the values of the 95% confidence interval (95% CI) boundaries were used. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results

The patients were admitted to the hospital in the first week of the disease. The patients who died from the disease had a complicated premorbid background, overweight and obesity, and coronary heart disease. Hypertension as a risk factor was present in more than 50% of the examined patients. Outpatient therapy with antiviral and antibacterial drugs was not carried out. The onset of the disease in all patients was acute with fever up to 39-41 °C, symptoms of intoxication, and catarrhal phenomena. Upon admission, the patients' condition was assessed as severe and extremely severe. The subjects were divided into two groups, comparable by age and gender: the first consisted of individuals with cardiovascular complications from influenza A/H1N1/09 (41 people), the second of patients without complicated influenza (45 people).

The average age of patients in the first group was 60 ± 13.7 years, the length of hospital stay was 15 bed-days. All patients had tachypnea with a respiratory rate of 23 ± 8.3 per minute. Saturation was $86.1 \pm 7.7\%$. According to the ECG results, sinus tachycardia with a heart rate of 94 ± 14.2 beats/min was predominant in combination with various rhythm and conduction disorders: acute (paroxysmal) form of atrial fibrillation in 19 (46%) patients, supraventricular extrasystole in 5 (12%), ventricular extrasystole in 7 (17%), complete left bundle branch block of His in 7 (17%), complete right bundle branch block in 7 (17%), first-degree atrioventricular block in one (2%) patient, and long QT syndrome in 5 (12%).

From the cardiovascular system, severe complications were observed: myopericardium 2 (5%) people had decompensation of chronic heart failure, 4 (10%) had decompensation of chronic heart failure, pulmonary embolism (PE) had one (2%), and acute myocardial infarction (AMI) had 11 (27%). Mortality in this group was 12 (29%) cases out of those hospitalized.

The average age of patients in the second group was 58 ± 14.1 years, the duration of hospital stay was 13 bed-days. All patients had tachypnea with a respiratory rate of 222 per minute. Saturation was $90.3 \pm 4.5\%$. According to the ECG results, sinus tachycardia with a heart rate of 91 ± 9.4 beats/min was detected in 98% of cases. Complete left bundle branch block (LBBB) was recorded in 3 patients (7%), atrial fibrillation in one (2%). No other rhythm and conduction disorders, as well as organic heart pathology were detected in this group of patients. The mortality rate was 5 (11%) people. When comparing the two groups, it can be concluded that mortality in the first group is significantly higher ($p = 0.0323$), the risk of death increases in the presence of cardiovascular complications in patients, OR 1.05 (95% CI 1.05-10.43).

Discussion

To identify individuals with severe community-acquired pneumonia, the American Thoracic Society / Infectious Diseases Society of America criteria, the SMART-COP scale and its modifications were used. Patients received antiviral drugs, antibiotics, additional respiratory support or artificial ventilation. Treatment of concomitant cardiac pathology was carried out with beta-blockers, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, antiarrhythmic and diuretic drugs, antiplatelet agents, and anticoagulants. Inclusion criteria for the study: adult patients of both sexes with a diagnosis of community-acquired pneumonia against the background of influenza A/H1N1/09, who did not receive outpatient therapy, and were not vaccinated against influenza. Exclusion criteria: pregnancy, the presence of acquired immunodeficiency syndrome and other immunodeficiency states.

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